

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

AVERAGES, ENTROPY AND OBSERVATIONS

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Abstract

This study discusses the probability $C_V(n)$ that the average of n independent random variables is closer to the distribution expectation than some of the variables. The article reveals that the probability $C_V(n)$ can be presented by a simple function of the standardized Normal distribution $N(0,1)$ entropy and the number of variables n . Simulations based on randomly generated numbers, derived from three Normal Distributions – $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 0.25)$, and $N(0, 9)$, and three Uniform Distributions – $U(-1, 1)$, $U(-2, 2)$, and $U(-10, 10)$ shows that the probability $C_V(n)$ is independent of the distribution standard deviation σ and $C_V(n) \rightarrow 0$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$. Simulations show, that the greatest probability to be an average closer to the distribution expectation μ than some observation in the sample, is when $n = 3$. However, even for the Uniform distribution, known to be the distribution with the greatest entropy, the probability $C_V(n=3) < 0.50$. Thus, automatically taking the mean of n observations as the most certain value of a measured quantity is risky and, in most cases, a wrong decision. More complicated approaches must be used to select the most trustful value among observations.

Keywords: Arithmetic Mean, Entropy, Normal Distribution, Number of observations, True Errors, Uniform Distribution

Introduction

According to the theory of measurements [9] and statistics [4], the accuracy $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ of the mean \bar{X} of n random measurements of a single quantity can be presented by equation (1) if the variance of measurements σ^2 is finite. The quantity $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ in engineering measurements is also a measure of uncertainty of the mean \bar{X} .

$$\sigma_{\bar{X}}^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{n} \quad (1)$$

This means that when $n \rightarrow \infty$ than $\sigma_{\bar{X}} \rightarrow 0$. The process of decreasing $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ with the increase of n is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Averages of n random numbers from $N(0, 1)$ distribution.

Looking at Figure 1, one can see that the amplitudes of the fluctuations of averages of n random normally distributed numbers are getting smaller. As a result, the averages approach the theoretical expectation of $N(0, 1)$ distribution of 0, and their true errors are getting smaller. One can also see that the true error of the aver-

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age of the first 27 random numbers is less than the average of the first 139 random numbers. According to the theory [4], the relationship (2) has to be valid and the uncertainty of \bar{X}_{139} to be less than that of \bar{X}_{27} , even though $\bar{X}_{139} \approx -0.026$ and $\bar{X}_{27} \approx -0.015$.

$$\sigma_{\bar{X}_{27}}^2 = \frac{\sigma^2}{27} > \frac{\sigma^2}{139} = \sigma_{\bar{X}_{139}}^2 \quad (2)$$

Based on the assumption that \bar{X}_{139} is twice more accurate than \bar{X}_{27} , the average \bar{X}_{139} will be preferred over \bar{X}_{27} in the routine engineering practice. However, such a choice could be the reason for the deterioration of the final results, which may reflect on making some wrong conclusions. Such a situation is illustrated in [3].

The main article objective is to estimate by generating random numbers from known distributions how often the original measurements have less true error than their average. In other words, we will know our expectations (true values). Because the uncertainty is associated with the entropy of the system in many disciplines, e.g., computer science [1], thermodynamics [2], medicine, biological sciences [6], etc., we will explore the relationship between the number of variables n , entropy of the used distributions, and the probability $Cv(n)$ that the average of the variables is closer to the distribution expectation than some of the variables.

Simulations

To estimate how often the average \bar{X} of n normally distributed random numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n is more closely located to the known expectation μ , we performed the experiment described below.

1. We generated matrix $NI(50000, 100)$ that contains 5000000 random numbers from the standard Normal distribution $N(0, 1)$. So, our initial matrix NI has the form (3).

$$NI = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1} & \dots & x_{1,100} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{50000,1} & \dots & x_{50000,100} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$NC1 = [Count(|NI|_{i,1} > |NS1|_{i,1}) \quad \dots \quad Count(|NI|_{i,100} > |NS1|_{i,100})] \quad (7)$$

5. Finally, we can find by dividing the members of matrix $NC1$ by 50000. Equation (8) presents these frequencies.

$$NF1 = [NC1_{1,1}/50000 \quad \dots \quad NC1_{1,100}/50000] \quad (8)$$

6. By repeating steps 1-5, we also calculated the frequencies of how often the mean \bar{X} of n normally distributed random numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n from $N(0, 0.25)$ and $N(0, 9)$ distributions are more closely located to the known expectation $\mu=0$.

7. We also performed the above procedure, steps 1-6, for Uniform distributions $U(-1, 1)$, $U(-2, 2)$ and $U(-10, 10)$.

Because we generated large samples of size $n=50000$, we can suppose that determined frequencies

2. Based on the numbers in matrix NI , we generated matrix $NS1$ with means from the first to J -th member for each row I , as shown below.

$$NS1 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=1} x_{1,j}}{k} & \dots & \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=100} x_{1,j}}{k} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=1} x_{50000,j}}{k} & \dots & \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=100} x_{50000,j}}{k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3. As next step, we prepared two matrices $|NI|$ and $|NS1|$ with absolute values of the members of NI and $NS1$ matrices, respectively.

$$|N1| = \begin{bmatrix} |x_{1,1}| & \dots & |x_{1,100}| \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ |x_{50000,1}| & \dots & |x_{50000,100}| \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$|NS1| = \begin{bmatrix} \left| \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=1} x_{1,j}}{k} \right| & \dots & \left| \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=100} x_{1,j}}{k} \right| \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \left| \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=1} x_{50000,j}}{k} \right| & \dots & \left| \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=100} x_{50000,j}}{k} \right| \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

4. By comparing the corresponding members of $|N1|$ and $|NS1|$, we generated matrix $NC1(1, 100)$ that counts in its column j the number of times when $|NI| > |NS1|$.

(8) fairly present the probability of the mean \bar{X} of n normally and uniformly distributed observations to be more accurate, that is to say, more closely located to the quantity true value, than some of the observations.

Results

Figures 2-5 illustrate the probabilities $Cv(n)$ obtained by simulations and calculated by equation (9). Table 1 contains the coefficients of equation (9).

$$Cv(n) = 0.25 \cdot \log_b(2\pi e) \cdot (n^{-c} - n^{-a}) \quad (9)$$

As can be seen from Figures 2-5, there is a functional relationship between the probability $Cv(n)$, the standardized Normal distribution $N(0, 1)$ entropy [8], and the number of observations n .

Figure 2: Probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Normal distributions – $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 0.25)$, and $N(0, 9)$, based on simulations of 50000 random numbers for each distribution and number n

Figure 3: Probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Uniform distributions – $U(-1, 1)$, $U(-2, 2)$, and $U(-10, 10)$, based on simulations of 50000 random numbers for each distribution and number n

Figure 4: Means of the probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Normal distributions – $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 0.25)$, and $N(0, 9)$ based on 150000 random numbers and the probabilities $Cv(n) = 0.25 \log_b(2\pi e) \cdot f(n, a, c)$

Figure 5: Means of the probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Uniform distributions – $U(-1, 1)$, $U(-2, 2)$, and $U(-10, 10)$ based on 150000 random numbers and the probabilities $Cv(n) = 0.25 \log_b(2\pi e) \cdot f(n, a, c)$

Table 1

Coefficients of the Probability Density Function of $Cv(n)$ distribution.

Distribution	Range	Probability Density Function of $Cv(n)$	Coefficients		
			b	a	c
Normal	n=1, 3, 4, ..., 40	$0.25 \cdot \log_b(2\pi e) \cdot (n^{-c} - n^{-a})$	3	$\sqrt{2\pi}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$
	n=2			$\sqrt{\pi}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$
	$41 \leq n \leq 100$		$\sqrt{2\pi}$	∞	$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} + \frac{1}{2} \right)$
Uniform	n=1, 4, ..., 50		$\sqrt{2\pi}$	$\sqrt{2\pi}$	$\frac{1}{e}$
	n=2				$\frac{1}{e}$
	n=3				$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$
	$51 \leq n \leq 100$				$\frac{1}{e}$
		$\sqrt{2\pi} + 0.00432 \cdot (n - 1)$	$\sqrt{2\pi}$	$\frac{1}{e}$	

Discussion

Figure 2 illustrates the probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Normal distributions — $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 0.25)$, and $N(0, 9)$ based on simulations of 50000 random numbers for each distribution and number. As can be seen, the probability density graphs of these distributions oscillate around each other in short ranges. If we increase the number of the generated random numbers, say from 50000 to 1000000, the probability density graphs will oscillate in shorter ranges or even cover each other. Thus, the probabilities $Cv(n)$ for Normal distributions are independent of the standard deviation of the distribution.

Figure 3 presents the same pattern of the probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Uniform distributions — $U(-1, 1)$, $U(-2, 2)$, and $U(-10, 10)$, but this time the values of $Cv(n)$ are slightly higher than that of the Normal distributions. This fact implies that the probability $Cv(n)$ is invariant of the variance of a distribution but depends on the distribution. The higher $Cv(n)$ values for given n can be explained by the highest entropy of the Uniform distribution among all known distributions [5].

Figure 4 shows the means of the probabilities $Cv(n)$ of the Normal distributions — $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 0.25)$, and $N(0, 9)$ based on 150000 random numbers and the probabilities $Cv(n)$ calculated by equation (9). A part of (9) is the expression (10), which is the entropy $H(N(0,1))$ of the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$ [8].

$$0.25 \cdot \log_b(2\pi e) = 0.5 \cdot 0.5 \cdot \log_b(2\pi e \cdot 1^2) = 0.5 \cdot H(N(0, 1)) \quad (10)$$

According to Table 1, the logarithm base varies depending on the number of observations n . Up to 40 observations $b = 3$, but if $n > 40$, then $b = \sqrt{2\pi}$. This can be explained by the fact that after the first 40 observations, there is a stabilization in the next averages. This explanation is clearly illustrated in Figure 1. One can see from Figure 4, that there is a full concordance between the results of simulations and forecasted values of $Cv(n)$. The coefficient of determination between both curves is $R^2 = 0.9992$. Therefore, there is a functional relationship between both curves.

According to Table 1 and Figure 4, when $n > 40$, we can rewrite (9) as (11).

$$Cv(n) \approx 0.77205 \cdot n^{-0.45} \approx 0.77205 / ^{2.222}\sqrt[n]{n} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) clearly shows that $Cv(n \rightarrow \infty) = 0$. Consequently, when the number of observations $n \rightarrow \infty$, the probability of the average of these n observations has less true error than some of the observations is close to 0. Thus, there is an observation that is more accurate than the average. The challenge for us is to find it.

Based on equations (1) and (11) we can find the relationship (12) between the probability $Cv(n)$, the entropy of the standard normal distribution with base $b = \sqrt{2\pi}$, and the standard deviation $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ of the average of n normally distributed observations with standard deviation σ when $n > 40$.

$$Cv(n) \approx 0.77205 / ^{2.222}\sqrt[n]{n} \approx 0.77205 \cdot ^{1.111}\sqrt[\sigma_{\bar{x}}]{\sigma} \quad (12)$$

A similar relationship to (12) can be obtained for the cases when $2 \leq n \leq 40$.

Analyzing Figure 5, we can see the same pattern as that in Figure 4. The only differences are the values of the parameters a , b , and c . The probability $Cv(n)$ low is the same. The above conclusions are also the same. The coefficient of determination between both curves of the probabilities $Cv(n)$ produced by simulations and calculated by equation (9) is $R^2 = 0.9983$. If we increase the number of randomly generated values, the coefficient of determination R^2 will increase. Thus, we found the same functional relationship between the probability $Cv(n)$, the entropy of the standard normal distribution, and the number n of uniformly distributed random numbers.

Conclusions

In the current article, the $Cv(n)$ distribution was presented. This distribution gives the probability of a sample mean having less true error than the sample observations. Simulations, based on random number generations from Normal and Uniform distributions showed that the peak of the $Cv(n)$ distribution for both distributions is when the number of observations $n=3$. Even then, the probability $Cv(n) < 0.5$. The last means that in the analyzed sample the probability of existing an observation with less true error than the mean is

greater than 50%. The probability density function of the $C_V(n)$ distribution shows that $C_V(n) \rightarrow 0$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$. In other words, when $n \rightarrow \infty$ then the probability of the existence of an observation with less true error than the mean tends to be 100%. Therefore, there is an opportunity to increase the accuracy and certainty of the processing data results by developing new algorithms for finding these observations that have fewer true errors than the mean. This task seems real, especially when there is a known mathematical rule between measured quantities, for example, the angles and their sum in a polygon.

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